

S2 Table. Schedule of the Brazilian Python Workshop for Biological Data in 2022.

Time	Day 1	Day 2		Day 3	Day 4	
8h30	Welcome	Presentation: Introduction to Python and its data structures	Reserved for group Exercises, questions and answers	Presentation: Results obtained in the group exercises	Presentation: What is Biopython?	
9h00	Live Coding - Introduction to Python and its data structures				Coffee-break	Live Coding - Autonomy for biological data analysis in Python
10h00				Live Coding - Introduction to Pandas and Matplotlib		
11h00						
12h00	Break			Break		
13h00	Talk: Eco-Evolutionary Simulation in Python	Talk: Running external programs with Subprocess lib		Reserved for group Exercises, questions and answers	Talk: Best practices and reproducibility of Python scripts	Talk: What is possible to do with python basics?
14h00	Live Coding - Introduction to Python and its data structures	Live Coding - Introduction to Pandas and Matplotlib			Live Coding - Autonomy for biological data analysis in Python	Flash Talks - Participants Projects
15h00		Coffee-break				
16h00		Live Coding - Introduction to Pandas and Matplotlib				
17h00 - 18h00		Questions and Answers				Questions and Answers